

Impact Report 2025

iMagine Impact Report – November 2025
imagine-ai.eu

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Interview With Gergely Sipos

EGI Foundation, iImagine Project Coordinator

Watch the interview here

youtube.com/watch?v=JVZb4eQk7OU

imagine-ai.eu

Introduction

The iImagine project was launched under the Horizon Europe programme with the mission to revolutionise how researchers monitor and understand aquatic ecosystems through advanced artificial intelligence (AI) and open science. Running from September 2022 to August 2025, iImagine has brought together a diverse consortium of partners spanning environmental sciences, data management, AI developments, e-infrastructures and Research Infrastructure. Its overarching objective: to bridge the gap between marine and freshwater research communities and cutting-edge digital technologies, creating a robust, open-access platform for AI-powered image analysis that serves both scientific and societal needs.

Through the development of new AI models, user-driven services, and a powerful cloud-based platform for AI model development, the project has empowered researchers to automate complex environmental assessments, accelerating insights and enabling real-time monitoring across freshwater and marine domains.

24

Partners

12

Research
Infrastructures
Supported

4

E-infrastructure
Providers

17

Use Cases
Supported

8

Key Exploitable
Results

4,5M

Funding

Relevant Links

iImagine Website

<https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

iImagine AI Platform

<https://go.egi.eu/imagine-ai-platform>

iImagine Zenodo Community

<https://go.egi.eu/imagine-zenodo-community>

iImagine YouTube Playlist

<https://go.egi.eu/imagine-youtube-playlist>

Check out all the partners and RIs that made iImagine possible at page 12.

iImagine Internal Use Cases

Marine Litter Assessment

This use case utilises AI-driven image analysis methods to automatically detect and quantify floating marine litter from drone imagery, aiming to enhance monitoring efforts for reducing plastic pollution in aquatic environments.

Zooscan

The Zooscan use case focused on applying AI techniques to classify and analyse zooplankton images captured by specialised imaging devices, to accelerate biodiversity assessments and ecosystem health monitoring.

EMSO Azores

This use case leveraged AI-based video and image analysis to monitor deep-sea hydrothermal vent ecosystems at the EMSO Azores observatory, aiming to automate the detection of biological and environmental changes over time.

EMSO OBSEA

At the EMSO OBSEA coastal observatory, this use case developed AI models to analyse underwater imagery for tracking marine life activity, supporting long-term ecological monitoring and habitat assessment.

EMSO Smartbay

Focusing on the EMSO Smartbay observatory, this use case developed AI models to process imagery and video from coastal waters and prawn burrow surveys. It aims to improve the automated detection of biological activity and develop models to assist in Prawn fisheries Surveys. EMSO Smart Bay also hopes to implement an existing Video Quality Assessment algorithm to review real-time and archived video data.

Oil Spill Detection

This use case applied AI models to satellite imagery to detect and predict the spread of oil spills at sea, supporting rapid response efforts and minimising environmental damage from marine pollution incidents.

FlowCam Phytoplankton Identification

The FlowCam use case developed AI algorithms to automatically identify and classify phytoplankton species from high-resolution microscope images, aiming to streamline water quality assessments and ecological studies.

Underwater Noise

This use case introduced AI methods to analyse hydrophone acoustic data for detecting and characterising underwater noise sources, aiming to support studies on the impact of human activities on marine ecosystems.

Beach Monitoring

The beach monitoring use case utilised AI models to automate beach seagrass wrack identification, shoreline extraction, and the detection of rip currents from beach imaging systems to improve coastal dynamics assessment and early warning systems development.

Freshwater Diatom Identification

This use case created AI models to classify freshwater diatom species from microscopic images, aiming to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of freshwater ecosystem biomonitoring programs.

iImagine External Use Cases

Cold Water Coral Reefs

Focusing on cold-water coral reef ecosystems, this use case used AI-driven image analysis to monitor reef health and detect changes over time, supporting biodiversity conservation efforts in deep-sea environments.

Satellite Derived Bathymetry

This use case applied AI techniques to satellite data to estimate underwater topography (bathymetry), aiming to provide faster and more cost-effective mapping of coastal and shallow marine areas.

Fish Otoliths

The fish otoliths use case developed AI tools to analyse the microscopic structures of fish ear bones (otoliths), aiming to automate species identification and support fisheries management and ecological research.

EyeOnWater

This use case enhanced the EyeOnWater citizen science platform by using AI to automatically validate smartphone images of water bodies, aiming to improve data quality and support large-scale environmental monitoring by the public.

Sea Wave and Coastal Inundation Detection Methodology

This use case introduced AI-based methods to detect sea wave patterns and coastal inundation events from sensor data and imagery, aiming to support early warning systems and coastal risk management strategies.

DEAL

The DEAL use case uses Swarm Learning to allow users to retain their image data and only share their models' parameters, making it possible for users to efficiently collaborate and improve models with lower biases, while preserving data privacy. In iImagine, DEAL can complement existing biodiversity capabilities while expanding the data available and allowing the team to verify and validate their cloud computing design requirements.

AI-based Detection and Classification of Seafloor Litter

This proof of concept evaluated the use of AI methods for the detection and classification of seafloor litter in deep-sea imagery retrieved from the Ifremer video archive and complemented with high-resolution mosaics produced during the 2023 and 2024 MOMARSAT cruises campaigns.

Key Results

Over the three years, the project has presented tangible instances and stories of success, bridged the gap between marine and freshwater research communities and cutting-edge digital technologies, and showcased the capabilities and potential of AI-powered image analysis to serve both scientific and societal needs. The project has contributed towards the Horizon Europe objectives with the following eight Key Results,

KER1:
Marine Litter Assessment

KER2:
Zooscan – Ecotaxa Pipeline

KER3:
Marine Ecosystem Monitoring

KER4:
Oil Spill Detection

KER5:
Flowcam Plankton Identification

KER6:
Prototype Imaging Services

KER7:
The iMagine AI Platform

KER8:
Best Practices

iImagine Impact

New Products and Services

iImagine AI Platform

The project's flagship product is the iImagine AI Platform, a cutting-edge computational platform designed to revolutionise image analysis in aquatic sciences. This platform was built as a generic, robust environment where users can develop, train, and share AI models for image processing at scale. It provides a one-stop solution covering the entire machine learning lifecycle – from data ingestion and annotation, through model training and validation, to deployment of models as ready-to-use services. The iImagine Platform is implemented on a federation of cloud resources (leveraging four cloud providers from the EGI federation) with on-demand GPU and CPU computing and large-scale storage to meet the intensive requirements of AI processing.

The platform is closely integrated with European-wide initiatives to maximise interoperability and user reach. As an open-access ecosystem, the iImagine platform will continue to enable researchers in aquatic science worldwide to develop, leverage and use advanced AI tools without needing to invest in their own compute infrastructure. This approach fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing across the community. The iImagine AI platform is expected to remain a lasting resource for the community, so that researchers across Europe can continue to access free at the point of use AI tools.

AI Models and Services

Building on this platform, iImagine developed a suite of AI services and models addressing specific scientific and environmental challenges. The project worked on over a dozen new image analysis services in collaboration with domain experts. These services cover a remarkably diverse range of aquatic science use cases, demonstrating the versatility of the platform. Together, this portfolio of AI services showcases how iImagine has operationalised AI for aquatic research.

The project delivered several ready-to-use AI models which are usable and retrainable by others. In addition, the project created accessible AI services that allow end-users

(such as marine researchers or environmental managers) to run complex image analyses on demand, without needing deep technical expertise. Other researchers and developers can build on these models and services to create domain-specific variants or adapt them for new environments. This facilitates the emergence of innovation cycles and derivative products. The project's models and software code for services are openly licensed and can therefore act as a springboard for future innovation. SMEs, startups, and service providers in the blue economy, environmental consulting, and geospatial analytics can adapt iImagine's services to deliver new commercial offerings without starting from scratch.

11,113,730

CPU-hours consumed

365,878

GPU-hours consumed

843 TByte

Month storage delivered

18

AI Models Developed

7

Mature AI Services

Impact on Science

Peer-reviewed Publications

Peer-reviewed scientific publications are a fundamental output of high-quality research, representing the formal channel through which new knowledge is validated, disseminated, and embedded into the broader body of scientific understanding. They serve not only as a record of innovation but also as a foundation for cumulative discovery, often sparking new lines of inquiry, shaping methodologies, and influencing how future research is conducted.

iImagine has generated a growing portfolio of peer-reviewed publications in high-impact journals and conference proceedings, spanning fields such as marine biology, remote sensing, computer vision, and environmental monitoring. These publications document the project's methodological innovations, for example, the development of deep learning models for plankton and diatom classification, AI-based tools for marine litter detection, and automated monitoring frameworks for acoustic noise and underwater ecosystems. In many cases, the publications are accompanied by open datasets and code repositories, enabling other researchers to reproduce, validate, and extend the work. This integrated approach — sharing models, data, and the scientific rationale — enhances the credibility and utility of iImagine's outputs. Publications also highlight collaborative, interdisciplinary approaches

involving environmental scientists, data engineers, and AI researchers, showcasing how cross-sector collaboration can deliver real-world innovation. By presenting novel AI methodologies and applications for environmental research, iImagine publications will inform and inspire future studies. Researchers working in related domains can reference these works to build on validated approaches or propose follow-up investigations. As these publications are cited in new articles, conference papers, and theses, iImagine's contributions will become embedded in the scientific canon, contributing to Europe's standing in AI and environmental science research.

Provision of Specifically Curated/edited Data

Provisioning of research data enables the research community, public and private entities to exploit these (digital) resources for their R&D or other purposes. These specifically curated datasets become a valuable resource to further develop products, innovations, studies, policies, etc.

iImagine has prioritised open data from the outset, producing and publishing multiple curated and annotated imaging datasets tailored to aquatic science. These datasets are hosted in trusted open-access repositories such as Zenodo and are designed to be reused by both

domain scientists and AI practitioners. These datasets have been formatted to meet FAIR standards, with comprehensive documentation, licenses, and persistent identifiers to support reuse and citation. Access to such clean, labelled data will lower the barrier to entry for new research. By openly sharing such large, domain-specific datasets, iImagine ensures that its scientific outputs can be diffused and reused by other researchers. These open datasets will also be valuable teaching tools in environmental science and AI curricula. Students and early-career researchers can use them in coursework or hackathons to gain practical experience with real-world data.

Changing Fundamentals of Research Practice

iImagine is a transformative research project that has not only created new knowledge but has also fundamentally changed the way research is conducted. The project has helped transform research practices in aquatic science.

iImagine has contributed to a fundamental evolution in aquatic and environmental research practices by promoting the shift from manual and fragmented workflows towards AI-enabled, automated, and standardised approaches. Historically, tasks such as taxonomic identification, organism counting, and image segmentation, among

others, relied heavily on time-consuming manual observation (e.g., delineation tasks) and the need for highly specialised personnel (e.g., ichthyologists). Data processing was often ad-hoc, non-standardised, and siloed within specific projects or institutions. iImagine has demonstrated that artificial intelligence, supported by open infrastructures, can automate and standardise these tasks at scale, drastically improving the efficiency, reproducibility, and objectivity of environmental monitoring. The project not only developed AI models and services but also systematically captured best practices, created training guidelines through its dedicated Competence Centre. This approach ensures that the knowledge is not locked within a single project participant but is accessible, reusable, and adaptable by researchers across Europe and beyond. By connecting imaging data processing directly with open science practices, iImagine has redefined how imaging data in aquatic sciences can and should be handled in the future. In doing so, it exemplified responsible, interoperable, and sustainable digital research practices, paving the way for broader adoption across disciplines.

16

Peer-Reviewed Publication

47

Conference Presentations

23

Datasets

2.3M+

Labelled Images

3

Best Practice Documents

1020

Views

990

Downloads

Creating and Shaping Scientific Networks

iImagine has made significant contributions to building new research networks and reinforcing existing collaborations. From the outset, iImagine was conceived as a highly collaborative initiative that linked multiple research infrastructures and initiatives. It brought together aquatic biologists, data providers, developers and AI specialists across more than 20 partner institutes, forging a network that spans disciplines and countries. To further its impact, iImagine also ran an open call to attract new use cases from the marine domain. The project's open call resulted in 6 new use cases, expanding not only its geographical but also its scientific reach.

Moreover, iImagine connected with external projects and international initiatives to exchange knowledge and avoid siloing of results. Notably, it integrated efforts with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the AI4EU (AI-on-Demand) platform to ensure its solutions align with broader e-infrastructure efforts. iImagine has also acted as a customer validation channel and source of user requirements for the

AI4EOSC platform. The project also partnered or shared outcomes with marine science networks like Blue-Cloud, data repositories like Zenodo and sister projects like ANERIS and AI4Life, multiplying the reach of its scientific innovations while providing an additional channel for exploitation of results coming out of these initiatives. These links mean that iImagine's scientific advancements (data, tools, standards) are being considered and potentially adopted by other major initiatives. These linkages ensured that the project was not working in isolation but contributing to a pan-European innovation ecosystem.

iImagine did more than deliver technologies. It has built bridges between people, institutions, and initiatives. These bridges will continue to serve as durable platforms for sustained scientific cooperation, enabling future co-creation, innovation, and policy influence. This enduring collaborative infrastructure ensures that iImagine's impact will continue to grow, not only through its direct outputs but also through the vibrant and dynamic networks it has helped shape.

zenodo

iImagine has been collaborating with Zenodo under the Horizon-ZEN project, which supports EC programme beneficiaries to comply with the FAIR and open science requirements. Thanks to this collaboration, Zenodo has added extra elements to its metadata template to fit the aquatic science datasets. These changes will persist beyond the project and will make Zenodo even more attractive for publishing marine datasets in future.

Skill Development

Competence Centre

The iImagine project had a strong focus on developing skills and human capital. At the centre of these efforts is the iImagine Competence Centre, a working group uniting AI experts, IT specialists, and aquatic scientists for continuous mutual learning. The Competence Centre convened regular meetings and annual workshops that provided coaching and support to all the project's use case teams. In these sessions, participants shared challenges and solutions, thereby learning from each other's experiences. The Competence Centre also proactively gathered input to create Best Practice guides, ensuring that the know-how gained was documented and shared with the broader community beyond the project.

This systematic approach to knowledge sharing meant that every partner improved their technical skills in AI and data handling throughout the project. Aquatic biologists learned about machine learning techniques through this collaborative environment, while computer scientists gained a deeper understanding of domain requirements – a two-way enrichment of skills. The Competence Centre and cross-RI collaboration model piloted by iImagine laid the groundwork for ongoing communities of practice, particularly around the development and governance of AI services, ensuring knowledge transfer continues well beyond the project's life.

Training and Higher Education Cooperation

iImagine also organised dedicated training activities to boost expertise. Internal training sessions and webinars were held on topics like image annotation, using the iImagine AI Platform, and data standardisation. A series of webinars introduced researchers to the platform's tools for AI model development, lowering the barrier for marine scientists to apply deep learning in their work. Finally, the project has also organised webinars for each of its services to showcase the capabilities and to share the outputs.

The project also engaged with higher education: some partners involved their graduate students and postdocs in iImagine's research, effectively training the next generation of interdisciplinary scientists.

In the FlowCam Phytoplankton Identification use case, a high school teacher introduced his students to using AI in marine science by demonstrating the phytoplankton classifier. After the students captured images using the PlanktoScope, the teacher used the OSCAR tool to predict the species.

SOCIB's Beach Monitoring use case engaged 2 BSc and 2 MSc students from diverse STEM fields (e.g., physics, informatics engineering). They received ML training, participated in developing open-access datasets, and used the iImagine platform for model development. This resulted in 2 completed BSc and 2 ongoing MSc theses focused on improving coastal monitoring using AI techniques, involving instance segmentation, oriented object detection, and semantic segmentation tasks.

FitSM Training

iImagine emphasised professional skills needed for sustaining its innovations. A notable achievement was providing FitSM training (Federated IT Service Management certification) to several project members. By getting researchers and technologists certified in FitSM, the project improved their ability to deliver reliable AI services to a broad user base following industry-standard processes. This not only benefited the individuals but also raised the overall quality of service delivery within iImagine.

Career Development

iImagine has and will continue to serve as a training ground for researchers, engineers, and technical staff, enhancing their skills, reputation, and career prospects. By providing training, mentorship, and hands-on experience, the project has contributed deeply to enhancing Europe's long-term research and innovation capacity. The researchers, engineers, and data specialists trained during the project will carry their enhanced skills into new endeavours across academia and industry, multiplying the impact of the training. They are now better equipped to lead and contribute to future AI projects. This increases their employability and strengthens their institutions' competitiveness in future funding calls.

Also, by lowering technical barriers and democratising access to AI workflows, iImagine has empowered researchers from varied disciplines and career stages. This inclusive approach helps diversify the innovation landscape, encouraging participation from underrepresented communities.

53
Meetings

3
Annual workshops

8
Webinars

+180
Participants

4
FitSM training sessions

15
Participants

Impact on Policy

Contributions to Open Science

iImagine has been exemplary in supporting open science and policy objectives. All of iImagine's research outputs (publications, datasets, software, and services) have been made publicly available and open access by default. By ensuring that its outputs are open access, iImagine contributes to European Commission policies that mandate or encourage open data and the FAIR principles in research.

The project adhered strictly to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) in data management, ensuring that its data and models can be easily found and reused by others. By depositing datasets and deliverables in open repositories (e.g., its community on Zenodo) and publishing in open-access journals, iImagine contributes to a culture of transparency.

This openness will advance science and support the European Commission's goals towards making publicly funded research accessible to all. The benefit is already visible: other researchers, outside the project, are already tapping into iImagine's outputs to build their work. Furthermore, the project's commitment to open-source development (where possible) means its software components can be inspected, validated, and extended by the community, increasing trust in the results. Such openness underpins trust in science by inviting scrutiny and collaboration, and iImagine's diligent application of FAIR and ethical guidelines ensures that its AI innovations were developed responsibly (for instance, avoiding bias in training data and respecting privacy). By rigorously applying the FAIR principles and making all results open access, iImagine actively promoted transparency, interoperability, and accountability in digital environmental monitoring.

Policy Development and Monitoring

iImagine has made a meaningful contribution to policy impact by producing openly accessible, evidence-based tools and services that directly support the monitoring and protection of aquatic environments. From its outset, the project aligned its objectives with pressing EU and global

policy agendas, including the EU Mission to Restore Our Oceans and Waters by 2030, the European Green Deal, the Zero Pollution Action Plan, and the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

From broad to detailed: evaluating AI in Marine Litter Monitoring

The developed service in the aquatic litter monitoring use case for litter assessment based on aerial imagery uses broader litter categories that are suitable for an automated classification using AI models. During the iImagine project, the partners conducted a study to assess whether the litter identification obtained by the AI-based system can be based on the detailed level of categories from the Joint List of Litter Categories for Marine Macrolitter Monitoring (J-codes list), which are commonly used in manual classification, and constitute the basic categorisation in assessment for policy purpose. The study compared two classification approaches: one performed automatically by the AI model using the original, less detailed categories, and the other conducted manually by humans using the detailed J-codes. The comparison of these two annotation methods revealed notable challenges in translating between the broad AI categories and the finer J-codes, and vice versa. These findings underscore the difficulties of implementing fine-grained litter classifications in automated systems and emphasise the need for continued research in this area.

Nonetheless, the developed service contributes to monitoring efforts by enabling broader spatial coverage and the collection of valuable data on plastic litter presence, offering an important step toward large-scale assessments, even if its categorisation does not align with the detailed standards used in manual classification.

iImagine's AI services offer operational tools that policymakers, environmental agencies, and monitoring bodies can adopt to measure progress, evaluate compliance, and respond to environmental risks. Public agencies and regulators now have access to these validated services that offer real-time, scalable alternatives to traditional methods, enabling more data-driven and proactive policy enforcement. Over time, as national governments, EU agencies, and global bodies continue to seek scalable, reliable, and cost-effective tools for environmental policy, the assets developed by iImagine — services, datasets, methodologies, and standards — are poised to play a strategic role in supporting evidence-based policy-making.

60+

Open research outputs

20

Software code pieces

Wider Impacts

Beyond scientific, human capital, innovation, and policy outcomes, iMagine has also left and will continue to leave socio-economic impacts on society and the economy

Citizen Science

Perhaps the most notable wider impacts of iMagine are in the area of public outreach and societal engagement. The project actively sought to involve and benefit stakeholders beyond the immediate research community. One of the key contributions to societal engagement in iMagine has been the integration of citizen science into advanced research workflows.

EyeOnWater

iMagine has strengthened the EyeOnWater citizen science initiative by integrating AI-based image validation into its app, which allows the public to assess water quality using smartphone photos. Using a YOLOv8 image classification model trained on over 13,000 labelled images, the system automatically filters user-submitted images into suitable categories for water quality analysis. This innovation has already processed more than 25,000 user images, with 66% deemed suitable, significantly reducing manual moderation and improving data reliability. By making the model openly available via the iMagine marketplace and GitHub, the project has boosted the scientific credibility and operational efficiency of EyeOnWater, demonstrating the practical value of AI in citizen-powered environmental monitoring.

DeepSeaSpy

In the EMSO Azores use case, iMagine is built on the DeepSeaSpy citizen science platform, which invites the public to annotate images of deep-sea marine fauna captured by underwater observatories. These citizen-labelled datasets were cleaned and processed through iMagine's AI pipeline to train models capable of automatically identifying deep-sea species. This approach not only enriched the training data with diverse real-world annotations but also reinforced the value of participatory science. By transforming volunteer contributions into robust AI inputs, iMagine bridged the gap between public engagement and cutting-edge deep-sea research, while raising awareness of ocean biodiversity and supporting scalable ecosystem monitoring.

Beach Monitoring – CoastSnap

iMagine's beach monitoring use case advanced the CoastSnap initiative, a global citizen science project that collects crowd-sourced beach photos to monitor shoreline changes in areas lacking traditional infrastructure. While highly valuable, CoastSnap's manual shoreline mapping methods were labour-intensive and limited in scalability. iMagine addressed this by publishing an annotated dataset of 1,700 images and testing machine learning models (e.g., BiLSTM, UNet) for automated shoreline segmentation. These efforts aim to reduce expert workload and accelerate data processing. The resulting AI tools will benefit coastal monitoring efforts in over 20 countries, making citizen science more efficient, responsive, and impactful for both researchers and coastal managers.

Local and Regional Impact

On the local and regional level, the project's activities have had positive effects as well. iMagine's consortium included institutes from coastal regions and technology hubs, and by securing European funding, these institutes were able to expand their operations and visibility. Hosting project meetings and training workshops in different locations brought together international experts, which benefited local venues and fostered regional pride in hosting cutting-edge scientific collaboration. Moreover, the collaborations seeded by iMagine are attracting follow-up projects and funding – for example, partners are now involved in new proposals building on iMagine's work, some of which bring additional investment to their regions. This clustering effect strengthens regional innovation ecosystems, a key aspect of how research can contribute to cohesion and development.

Indirect Impacts

Finally, the nature of iMagine's work means it has an environmental and societal benefit that, while indirect, is significant. By equipping researchers with better tools to monitor and understand aquatic ecosystems, iMagine contributes to society's capacity to manage environmental challenges. Over time, this can lead to healthier oceans and waterways, which means safer food from the sea, preserved biodiversity, and more resilient communities against climate impacts. These are benefits that every citizen can ultimately experience, aligning with broader societal goals.

iImagine Made Possible By

Partners

Related RIs

imagine-ai.eu